

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CNT/CARBON FIBER/EPOXY HIERARCHICAL COMPOSITES PREPARED USING ELECTROPHORETIC DEPOSITION

Shan Li¹, Shinn-Shyong Tzeng^{2*}, Ding-Hwa Cherng³ and Hsien-Tang Chiu⁴

¹Graduate Institute of Applied Science and Technology, National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, No. 43, Sec.4, Keelung Rd., Taipei 106, Taiwan
Email: lshan@ms25.hinet.net

²Department of Materials Engineering, Tatung University
7-1 Teh-Hui Street, Taipei 104, Taiwan
Email: sstzeng@ttu.edu.tw

³Department of Materials Engineering, Tatung University
7-1 Teh-Hui Street, Taipei 104, Taiwan
Email: tony155034@hotmail.com

⁴Department of Materials Science and Engineering, National Taiwan University of Science and Technology, No. 43, Sec.4, Keelung Rd., Taipei 106, Taiwan
Email: hchiu@mail.ntust.edu.tw

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ABSTRACT

CNTs with a diameter of ~10-50 nm were deposited on the surface of carbon fiber (CF) fabrics using electrophoretic deposition (EPD). Then the CNT/CF fabric were impregnated with the epoxy resin and the vacuum bag hot pressing technique was used to fabricate the CNT/CF/epoxy three-phase hierarchical composites. Two different processes were used in the preparation of the electrophoretic solution. The first approach used the surfactant (NaDDBS or SDS) to disperse the CNTs in the DI water with the aid of ultrasonic input. The second process involved the modification of CNTs with polyethyleneimine (PEI) and then the electrophoretic solution was prepared through the sonication of aqueous solution containing PEI-treated CNTs. The experimental results of flexural test indicated that both the flexural strength and modulus decreased with the addition of CNTs by EPD using NaDDBS or SDS as the surfactant. On the other hand, enhancement of both the flexural strength and modulus was measured for the incorporation of PEI-treated CNTs. A 36% increase of flexural strength can be achieved. Although relatively uniform coverage of CNTs on the surface of CF fabric in EPD using the surfactant can be observed in the SEM images, damage of CF surface due to electrochemical etching was found during EPD. Single fiber tensile tests were performed for CFs before and after EPD and the results showed degradation of fiber strength when using NaDDBS or SDS as the surfactant. However, similar fiber strength was obtained after EPD when using PEI-treated CNTs. TGA results also showed lower oxidation temperatures for CFs after EPD using NaDDBS or SDS as the surfactant and similar oxidation temperature as compared with that of as-received CFs was measured for CFs after EPD when using PEI-treated CNTs.

1 INTRODUCTION

The superior mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and carbon nanofibers (CNFs) make them the ideal candidates for composite reinforcement. Although some experimental measurements indicated the enhancement of strength with the addition of CNTs into the polymer matrix [1-4], results without or with limited strength enhancement were also reported [3,4]. Two important issues concerning the applications of CNTs and CNFs in the composite reinforcement need

to be overcome. The first is the uniform dispersion of these nano-reinforcing materials in the polymer matrix. The second is the effective stress transfer from the CNTs to the composite. For the effective stress transfer, the bonding between the reinforcement and the matrix should be strong, which make the surface properties of the CNTs and CNFs important.

Recently, incorporation of CNTs or CNFs in carbon fiber(CF)/polymer composites to form a hybrid multiscale composite was proposed and enhancements of mechanical behavior were reported [5-9]. The properties of carbon nanomaterials based composites primarily depend on the dispersion of nanomaterials in the matrix of composites. Agglomeration of nanofillers leads to the generation of potential defects and thereby deteriorates composite properties. Hence the selection of an efficient dispersion technique for nanofillers prior to the fabrication of three-phase composites is extremely important. To date, four major approaches have been developed [10, 11]: (1) infusion of a CNT/resin mixture into the preform, (2) direct growth of CNTs on reinforcement fabric substrates, (3) direct placement of CNTs between layers of the preform, and (4) electrophoretic deposition (EPD) of CNTs on reinforcement fabric substrates. Discussion of these methods can be found in the literature [10, 11]. In this investigation, CNT reinforced three-phase composites (CNT/CF/epoxy) were fabricated using EPD and their mechanical behavior was investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 EPD process and fabrication of composites

CNTs were deposited on the surface of CF fabrics using EPD before the fabrication of hybrid composites. Multi-walled CNTs with a diameter of ~10-50 nm were used, and a 3k plain-woven PAN-based CF fabric, manufactured from Taiwan Formosa Company, was adopted for the micro-sized reinforcement. Two different processes were used in the preparation of the electrophoretic solution. The first approach used the surfactant (NaDDBS (sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate) or SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate)) to disperse the CNTs in the DI water with the aid of ultrasonic input. The second process involved the modification of CNTs with polyethyleneimine (PEI) [12] and then the electrophoretic solution was prepared through the sonication of aqueous solution containing PEI-treated CNTs. After the deposition of CNTs on the surface of CF fabric (CNT/CF fabric), the CNT/CF fabric were impregnated with the epoxy resin and the vacuum bag hot pressing technique was used to fabricate the CNT/CF/epoxy three-phase hierarchical composites.

2.2 Characterization

The mechanical properties and fracture behavior were studied using the three-point bending test according to ASTM D-790. The fracture surfaces of the composites after bending tests were observed using SEM. For the characterization of CFs before and after the EPD process, in addition to the SEM observation of the surface morphology, single fiber tensile test was used to measure the fiber strength using a universal testing machine (Shimadzu) with a load cell of 1 N. Also, the TGA analysis in the air atmosphere was adopted to assess the damage of CFs by measure the oxidation temperature of CFs before and after the EPD process.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology after EPD process

Fig. 1 shows the SEM images of the CF fabric after EPD of CNTs at a constant voltage of 15V. Relatively uniform coverage of CNTs on the surface of CF fabric can be observed in the SEM images of lower magnification (Fig. 1(a) and 1(b)), although some fibers were not coated with CNTs as shown in the higher magnification image (Fig. 1(c)).

The SEM images of the CFs using different processes in the preparation of the electrophoretic solution are presented in Fig. 2. As compared with Figure 1 at a deposition voltage of 15V, quite uniform CNT coverage could be still observed at 10 V using NaDDBS as the surfactant (Figure 2(a) and 2(b)). However, CNT aggregation can be found frequently for both samples. The CNT coverage was less uniform when using SDS as the surfactant (Figure 2(c) and 2(d)). The deposition was mainly

located at the gaps between CFs. Different deposition morphology was observed when using PEI-treated CNTs (Figure 2(e) and 2(f)). The CNTs deposited on the CF surface were covered with a polymer-like material, presumably PEI. The coverage of PEI-treated CNTs was more uniform as compared with those using NaDDBS or SDS as the surfactant.

Figure 1: SEM images of CNT-coated CF fabrics using EPD at a constant voltage of 15V.

Figure 2: SEM images of CNT-coated CFs using different processes in the preparation of the electrophoretic solution: (a)(b) using NaDDBS as the surfactant; (c)(d) using SDS as the surfactant; (e)(f) using PEI-treated CNTs. The deposition voltage was 10V.

3.2 Mechanical properties of the hybrid composites

The results of flexural strength and modulus of CNT/CF fabric/epoxy three-phase hierarchical composites are presented in Fig. 3. As shown in Fig. 3, both the flexural strength and modulus can be enhanced when the composites were reinforced with PEI-treated CNTs. It is noted that a decrease of EPD duration from 1 hour to 20 min resulted in an increase of both flexural strength and modulus, indicating that there is an optimum amount of CNT addition. A 36% increase in flexural strength can be obtained in the present investigation. On the other hand, both the flexural strength and modulus were found to decrease when CNTs were deposited using NaDDBS or SDS as a surfactant. To clarify the reason for the strength variation, the fracture surfaces of the hierarchical composites were observed using SEM and are presented in Figure 4 (using NaDDBS) and Figure 5 (using SDS). CNTs can be found in the interlayer regions in both composites (Figure 4 and Figure 5). Also, from Figure 4 it seems that good bonding was observed in the interface between layers due to the presence of CNTs.

Figure 3: Mechanical properties of CNT/CF fabric/epoxy three-phase hierarchical composites prepared using different EPD conditions: (a) flexural strength and (b) flexural modulus.

Figure 4: SEM images of the fracture surfaces of CNT/CF fabric/epoxy three-phase hierarchical composites prepared using NaDDBS as the surfactant for the EPD process.

Figure 5: SEM images of the fracture surfaces of CNT/CF fabric/epoxy three-phase hierarchical composites prepared using SDS as the surfactant for the EPD process.

3.3 Characterization of fibers after EPD process

To further clarify the reason for the decrease of flexural strength, the CF fabrics were examined using SEM before and after the EPD process and the results are shown in Figure 6. Although the surface striations along the fiber axis can be seen for the as-received CFs (Figure 6(a)), they showed relatively smooth surface as compared with that of CFs after desizing (Figure 6(b)). The surface striations were revealed more clearly after desizing. Figure 6(c) and 6(d) shows the surface morphology of CFs after the EPD process (no CNTs added in the electrophoretic solution) using SDS

and NaDDBS as the surfactant, respectively. It is noted that the grooves along the fiber axis are not the original surface striations developed from the fiber production. The wider and deeper grooves can be found on the CF surfaces after the EPD process. While a more detailed understanding is required, it is speculated that the wider and deeper grooves were resulted from the electrochemical etching during the EPD process when the SDS or NaDDBS was used as the surfactant. Contrary to the EPD process using SDS or NaDDBS as the surfactant, the wider and deeper grooves were not observed on the surface of CFs when PEI was used in the EPD process (Figure 6(e)). However, deposition of PEI on the surface was found.

Figure 6: SEM images of CFs: (a) as received, (b) after desizing, (c) after the EPD using NaDDBS as the surfactant, (d) after the EPD using SDS as the surfactant, and (e) after the EPD using PEI-treated CNTs.

Single fiber tensile tests were also performed to characterize the fiber damages from the EPD process and the results are presented as the Weibull plot in Figure 7. As shown, desizing of CFs lowered the fiber strength quite obviously. The reason can be attributed to the filling of the surface striations by the sizing polymer as supported by the more clearer surface striations after desizing (Figure 6(a) and 6(b)). The surface striations could serve as the strength-limiting defects, which will reduce the strength significantly especially for brittle materials. Further reduction of the fiber strength was also observed for CFs after the EPD process using SDS or NaDDBS as the surfactant, which is consistent with the SEM observation of wider and deeper grooves after the EPD process. On the other hand, enhancement of fiber strength as compared with that of CFs after desizing was measured for CFs after the EPD process using PEI. The reason is presumably the partial filling of the surface striations by PEI.

Figure 7: Weibull plots of CFs before and after the EPD process.

TGA analysis of CFs before and after the EPD process is also consistent with the above strength measurements and SEM observation, and is presented in Figure 8. The results clearly indicated that the oxidation temperature of CFs decreased after the EPD process using SDS or NaDDBS as the surfactant due to the electrochemical etching as explained previously. On the other hand, similar oxidation temperatures were measured for as-received, desizing and PEI-treated CFs.

Although more characterizations are still needed, the decrease of fiber strength after the EPD process using SDS or NaDDBS as the surfactant is thought to be one of the major reasons resulting in the reduction of the flexural strength and modulus of the CNT/CF fabric/epoxy three-phase hierarchical composites as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 8: TGA curves of CFs before and after the EPD process.

4 CONCLUSIONS

CNT/CF fabric/epoxy three-phase hierarchical composites were fabricated and the mechanical properties of the three-phase composites were investigated. The EPD technique was used to deposit the CNTs on the surface of CFs before the composite fabrication. Two different processes were used in the preparation of the electrophoretic solution. The first approach used the surfactant (NaDDBS or SDS) to disperse the CNTs in the DI water with the aid of ultrasonic input. The second process involved the modification of CNTs with PEI and then the electrophoretic solution was prepared through the sonication of aqueous solution containing PEI-treated CNTs. Reduction of the flexural strength and modulus of the composites was measured when NaDDBS or SDS was used as the surfactant in the EPD process. Results of SEM observation, single fiber tensile tests and the TGA analysis indicated that the electrochemical etching of the CFs during the EPD process when using SDS or NaDDBS as the surfactant led to the decrease of the fiber strength, which was responsible for the strength loss of the composites. On the other hand, enhancement of both the flexural strength and modulus was measured for the incorporation of PEI-treated CNTs. A 36% increase of flexural strength can be achieved.

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